

ISic1412

I.Sicily inscription 1412

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

breccia

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2006.04; 2018.07.05

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Haluntium

Place of origin (modern)

San Marco d'Alunzio

Provenance

Recovered during restoration work in the 1950s or 1960s on the campanile of the Chiesa San Nicolo di Bari

Coordinates

38.073915, 14.699100

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, S. Marco d'Alunzio, Museo della cultura e delle Arti Figurative Bizantine e Normanne, inventory 5

Physical Description

A thick rectangular slab of the local breccia di San Marco (a pink/red stone with white veins), broken in the upper right corner. There is a circular round hole in the top surface.

Dimensions

Height 73 cm

Width 58 cm

Depth 16 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-5: 13-15 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐπὶ ἱερομνάμονος Σα[ν]νίω[νος τοῦδεῖνα]
2. ἀγνωθετᾶν Κλεάνδρου τοῦ Αρ[---]
3. Παρμ[---][τοῦ][---]
4. Ζώιλου τοῦ Θέστ[ωνος---
5. λαμπαδιστ[αί][---]

Apparatus

Text of Manganaro 1999

Translation

Commentary

One of two inscr. on this block. The other inscription ISic2937 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic2937>] on the top surface appears approximately contemporary and is also apparently of gymnasial relevance. The text requires minor revision in light of further autopsy

Digital identifiers:

TM 644963

EDCS 70900810

PHI 330045

PHI 336065

Bibliography

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